

Journey to the cloud: A case study of digital business transformation

Dr. Pearl Guterman^a

^a*Toronto, ON, Canada*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Cloud-based platforms can greatly enhance a company's digital capabilities from transaction management to real-time analytics—so much so that adoption and migration is not a matter of if but when! While the benefits of the cloud are clear, the journey to the cloud can be complex.

2. Aim

To provide practical insights into a Fortune 100 company's successful migration from legacy applications to the cloud.

3. Material and methods

The Accenture Insights Platform (AIP), Amazon Web Services (AWS), and other services for data management, analytics and reporting, were used to build a cloud-based, self-service analytics portal for a pharmaceutical and consumer products company. Functional and technical requirements were assessed to tailor a holistic solution that maximized value from the cloud while enabling a smooth transition from a legacy platform.

4. Results

Acceleration of data-driven business decisions as a result of leveraging a fast and easily scalable, cloud-based datalake and dynamic reporting solutions.

5. Conclusions

Every cloud journey is different. The key to a successful migration includes a tailored approach that ensures the right partnerships to make the journey a smooth, agile, and rewarding one.

January 22, 2018

6. Keywords

AIP; AWS; Cloud computing; Analytics; Migration

Author biography

Dr. Pearl Guterman Data Science Lead at Accenture